

ALL-ATLANTIC OCEAN RESEARCH
AND INNOVATION ALLIANCE

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2024 Intergenerational Dialogue Session

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All-Atlantic Community Voices

2024 Intergenerational Dialogue

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Executive Summary

The initiative “All-Atlantic Community Voices”, presented at the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA) Forum 2024, is a digital platform to empower local actors of coastal communities across the Atlantic to take a leading role in identifying challenges and co-creating solutions according to their specific and shared needs and situations allowing local actors from different regions to transfer and adapt tested methods to specific settings. The platform would provide an open space for communities to express their specific challenges and actively and jointly seek, build and share knowledge, tools, experience and solutions through international collaboration forming an interconnected, diverse, grass-roots Atlantic community of Practice. Some of the highlight features of the All-Atlantic Community Voices Platform include:

- Coastal Communities exchange their specific challenges and needs.
- Knowledge transfer between communities on lessons learned and best practices.
- Co-creation of solutions designed by the Community of Practice.
- Mutual capacity building, upskilling/skill-sharing, training & recruitment.
- Enhanced international collaboration, partnerships and engaged citizenship.

The "All-Atlantic Community Voices" platform fosters a bottom-up approach, the initiative strengthens local resilience, enhances capacity development, and promotes more inclusive, sustainable ocean governance across the Atlantic.

Policy brief

Introduction

The intergenerational dialogue side event was a key feature of the 2024 All-Atlantic Ocean Research & Innovation (AAOIRA) Forum, fostering necessary exchanges between Early Career Ocean Professionals (ECOPs) and experienced academics. Ocean stakeholders from Atlantic basin countries gathered to discuss opportunities for knowledge sharing, research collaboration, innovation and cooperation, focusing on coastal resilience, ocean modelling and crosscutting research themes. This session decisively amplified the voices of early-career researchers, showcasing their expertise and innovative ideas in ocean-related policymaking.

All-Atlantic Community Voices platform

The All-Atlantic Community Voices platform (hereafter referred to as "Community Voices") is conceptualised around co-design, co-creation, and co-implementation. The platform was posited as an opportunity to encourage grassroots, local actor-driven needs identification, knowledge-sharing and opportunity amplification. Community Voices aims to provide communities with a space to make known the challenges they face and to connect with, learn from, and build partnerships with, other Atlantic communities dealing with similar issues. This bottom-up approach focuses on active participation of communities to engage with each other in a cooperative, multisectoral manner.

Aside from building resilience through connectivity, an additional benefit is the reduced need for measures imposed by international policies and scientific projects which may deliver on directional guidance, innovation and new tools, but often lack the appropriate dialogue with coastal communities. This platform addresses a vital gap in the connectivity of Atlantic coastal communities. Coastal communities have increasingly been facing various challenges including, but not limited to, sea-level rise, extreme weather events, coastal erosion, habitat degradation and the loss of ecosystem services, changes to fishery and aquaculture conditions, and anthropogenic contamination leading to polluted environments.

Meanwhile, many coastal communities are implementing measures through scientific innovations, policy-level measures, and citizen-based activities to address these challenges in specific case sites and seeing positive results or learning lessons from measures not deemed effective, or with unexpected consequential impacts. Already, some local actors in coastal communities are working with scientists, engineers, geographers and decision-makers to identify solutions for their problems. However, these problems are not unique, and coastal communities are facing similar threats globally.

There exists a gap between those groups who face similar challenges, between those who are implementing solutions, and those who are seeking experienced knowledge. Likewise, between those specific skills, resources, tools, and capacities which are needed, and those which have them to offer and seeking collaboration, employment, or expansion opportunities. This is the connectivity gap which Community Voices aims to address. The proposed platform can bridge these gaps, offering a forum for connecting with other actors and communities with similar problems, to share needs, find opportunities, and offer support. Another barrier which will be tackled in this approach is to overcome language and communication problems. By establishing an AI real-time translation algorithm within the platform languages will be detected and translated immediately providing accessibility to everyone. It is also envisioned that platform user training would be offered to local entities such as environmental agencies, managers, port authorities, industry representatives, fishery spokespeople, so that the benefits of the platform can reach those who otherwise might not be able to access due to infrastructure, technology-use capacity, or other undocumented barriers.

Platform Benefits:

- Activated network of Coastal Resilience actors: empowering community-driven solutions across the Atlantic to take the lead in expressing needs and co-developing solutions.
- Collection & Sharing of Good Practices: knowledge-sharing encourages communities mutual knowledge building and learning from each other and sharing of practices.
- Partnerships, Enterprise & Employment: economic opportunities to facilitate professional advancement - job-finding, opportunity-sharing, skill development and international partnership.

Figure 1. Schematic pathway of growth for the Community of Practice as presented to the AAORIA High-Level Board. From left to right, the image shows the transition from a) an Atlantic basin without a platform for community voice, to b) the platform with some examples of the proposed users with complementary needs and opportunities to c) a connected All-Atlantic community where knowledge, skills, resources, and opportunities can be shared for improved partnerships and collaboration.

Key Output

Key outputs from Community Voices will firstly be an inspirational repository of community-actions for resilience, showcasing which efforts, innovations and solutions are being tested, implemented and scaled up, and the networks being constructed to support them. This repository would primarily serve other coastal local actors and stakeholders (in a "by communities, for communities" fashion), but it would also serve the academic and policy-making communities as a valuable and effective database of the Community of Practice. The envisioned outcome would include an established basin-wide network of users, wherein resources, tools and opportunities can be shared and utilised, facilitating interconnectedness and knowledge-transfer. With the right ambition, outcomes can be expanded to include features such as early-warning hazard risk reduction, valuation of the blue economy and of nature-based solutions, and the advancement of Ocean Literacy, citizen science and participatory citizenship. Once implemented and established, Community Voices has an envisioned impact of building a strengthened, connected, empowered, engaged community of people across the Atlantic, this impact could be considered a sense of friendship and neighbourliness pole-to-pole, east to west, with communities working together to address shared and unique problems, with the potential of being extended globally and realising the spirit of "Think Global, Act Local".

Outputs:

Who, What, Where, How,
of Community-led
Resilience

Outcome:

Activated network of Coastal
Resilience actors.
Partnerships, Enterprise
& Employment

Impact:

Strengthened
Community of Atlantic
People

Ambition: Early warning hazard risk reduction, valuation of blue economy and Nature Based Solutions, Ocean Literacy & citizen engagement, participative Atlantic citizenship

Figure 2. The expects outputs, outcomes, and impact of the All-Atlantic Community Voices initiative. The data on regional actions, innovations, and experiences will feed into the network allowing for the construction of resources such as toolboxes, use-cases, network-building tools, and search engines for opportunities. These resources constructed by and for the Community of Practice will strengthen connections around the Atlantic and allow for the testing, upscaling, and establishment of effective solutions.

Conclusions

The Intergenerational Dialogue session at the 2024 All-Atlantic Ocean Research & Innovation Forum underscored important steps taken toward strengthening coastal resilience, climate adaptation, and biodiversity preservation. The formal introduction of Iceland and Senegal expanded the alliance's membership. Key initiatives launched included the OKEANO Coastal Resilience Knowledge Hub to support adaptation strategies and the enhancement of ocean observation networks across the Atlantic. Discussions promoted cooperation across borders and especially welcomed the involvement of ECOPs. The outcomes aim to shape future sustainable practices and research priorities, with the next forum to be hosted by the European Union in 2025.

AAORIA Forum established a vital platform for engaging early-career ocean professionals (ECOPs) in meaningful exchanges across generations. It amplified their voices and highlighted their expertise and innovative ideas in ocean policymaking, utilising Atlantic Basin projects to guide future collaborations. The session promoted inclusivity and diversity by involving a wider range of stakeholders. Community Voices is a key output which emphasises the importance of building ocean and coastal resilience and advocates for community-driven, bottom-up approaches to empower local solutions in ocean research.

Recommendations

- Leverage Atlantic Basin projects and use the insights from showcased Atlantic Basin projects to guide future cooperation and collaborative initiatives in the Atlantic region.
- Support community-driven solutions, via bottom-up approaches, to empower communities and promote inclusion, equity, and diversity in ocean research by multiple stakeholders' participation.
- Develop synergies for need-opportunity gap bridging. This would include establishing thematic areas for the Community of Practice, so users who face similar issues can connect easily with each other and with users who can provide tools, skills, experience to collectively address issues.
- Build a Coastal Resilience Training and Employment forum within the Community Voices platform so that opportunities for skills growth, capacity development, higher learning, and professional services can be offered, advertised, or sought.
- Build a Coastal Resilience Educational Forum where learners and educators can share knowledge directly, find relevant content and digital resources for teaching and learning, interact with scientists and policymakers, and enhance ocean literacy with a specific focus on impacts and opportunities for coastal communities.

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All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance

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